

There is No Such Thing as a Composite Material – Only Composites *of* Materials

by

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Outline

THE PROBLEM:

Unanticipated failures in polymer matrices often precede failures in fibres, thereby preventing the laminates from attaining their expected strengths or causing a need for excessive inspections and repairs.

THE CHALLENGE:

To break the unfounded belief in matrix failure predictions prepared on the assumption of *homogenized* plies, and to create an awareness of the need to think of fibre/polymer composites as *heterogeneous* composites of materials.

ILLUSTRATIONS OF THE NEED FOR IMPROVED ANALYSIS CAPABILITY:

Several examples are shown of matrix failures that preceded fibre failures to prove that the need for improved scientific analyses is real.

FEATURES NEEDING TO BE INCLUDED IN CONSTITUENT-LEVEL ANALYSES CAPABLE OF PREDICTING MATRIX FAILURES. THE SIFT (STRAIN INVARIANT FAILURE THEORY) CRITERIA:

Explanations of the limitations of homogenized-laminae analyses. Explanation of SIFT failure theory for composites as the only known theory capable of *predicting* matrix failures, as distinct from *interpolating* empirically.

Shrinkage of Resin Matrix Around Fibres

Two Most Common Design Defects in Fibre/Polymer Composite Structures

$$k_t = 1 + \frac{A_{\text{stringer}}}{t_{\text{stringer}} \times t_{\text{skin}}} \text{ in general, } k_t = 1 + \frac{h_{\text{stringer}}}{t_{\text{skin}}} \text{ for blade stiffeners}$$

Premature Failure of Stepped-Lap Bonded Joint by Delamination

Initial failure occurred at "A" because thickness "B" is excessive and load in fibres at "C" cannot be unloaded through the resin matrix.

Final failure at "D" is by net-section tension on the top face and shear-out (not shown) on the lower surface.

Skin Delaminations Caused by Segmenting Co-Cured Composite Stringers, and a Possible Design Solution to the Problem

Simple Composite Frame/Stringer Intersection with No Loss of Axial Continuity in Either Member

Features of the Hollow-Hat Section Bonded Beaded Composite Stringer

Improved Secondarily Bonded Design for Large Aircraft Tail Cone, of Far Lower Cost than Original Co-Cured Design

One-piece unstiffened composite skin

Secondarily bonded lattices of stiffening beads

Composite Tail-Cone,
Looking Aft

Sheet-metal frames

C-section machined intercostals

Z-section sheet-metal intercostals

Secondarily bonded lattices of stiffening beads

Metallic Substructure,
Bottom Half Pre-Assembled

Identification of Weak Resin Interface between Composite Members of Structure

Skin-Doubler Combination: All the load carried in the doubler can pass to or from the skin *ONLY* through the thin resin interface.

Inherent Difficulty in Modelling Interfacial Hot Spots Using Finite-Element Analyses

No singularities predicted. No warning of potential problems in highly loaded resin interface that was omitted from model. Needs post-processing with more realistic details to be able to characterize behaviour of resin matrix.

**Finite Elements in Conventional Coarse First Analysis
for Large Structures, Masking Existence of Interfaces**

Artificial singularities predicted here because
load in doubler *must* drop to zero at the ends.

Additional Finite Elements in More Realistic Analysis for Large Structures

*Artificial in the sense that the singularity exists only in the model, NOT in the real structure.

Need to Include Discrete Interlayer in Finite Element Model to Be Able to Quantify Finite Peak Interfacial Stresses and Strains

Flexible Layer Added Between Skin and Doubler Enables Relative Motion to Avoid Predicting Artificial Singularities at Ends of Doubler

Flexible interlayer needs to be modelled only between points *A* and *B*, because the skin and doubler strain together in the interior, *A* to *A*.

The Best Way to Eliminate Premature Matrix Failures in Fibre/Polymer Composites

Eliminate the design features that cause delaminations, no matter what the alleged benefit from not doing so.

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This is best accomplished through empirical wisdom, which used to exist and which can be recovered, not by after-the-fact analyses and supplemental inspections when it is too late for design and manufacturing changes,.

Doing so requires an acknowledgement that fibre/polymer composites are heterogeneous, not homogeneous.

Integrate the design and manufacturing approaches simultaneously, not sequentially.

Progressively Enhanced Definitions of Stresses and Strains In Composite Laminates

Coarsest Level, Finite Element Model

Homogenized Element of Laminate

Accurate for representing overall *stiffnesses*, and resultant forces and moments, but inherently incapable of predicting failure in either fibres or the resin matrix

Ply-by-Ply Decomposition

Individual Layers of the Laminate, One Homogenized Lamina at a Time

Possibility of predicting many fibre failures accurately, when used in conjunction with non-interactive failure models. No possibility of predicting matrix failures when using measured lamina-level strengths, other than by using new properties for each fibre volume fraction and operating temperature, *and* by differentiating between modes of matrix failures non-interactively

Micro-mechanical Enhancement for Each Individual Ply

Individual Fibre and Resin Constituents

Only possibility of predicting all fibre *and* matrix failures accurately, when used in conjunction with physics-based failure model, like SIFT, with universal properties for all fibre volume fractions and operating temperatures

Micromechanical Models to Relate Lamina and Constituent-level Strains

Mechanical and Thermal Strains Included, at *Both* Lamina and Constituent Levels

Variable Stresses,
Uniform Interior Axial
Strain,
 $E_1 = \text{Constant}$

Variable Strain, Stress-free
Surface,
 $S_1 = 0$

Fibre Reference Axes

Fibre

Resin

Strains and Strain
Invariants Computed for
Fine (Converged) Grid
Within Fibres And Resin

Lamina-level Strains,
Assumed to Be
Uniform with Respect
to These Dimensions

(Thermally Induced Strains Computed with
Respect to States of Free Contraction of
Disconnected Resin and Fibres)

Unit Cell Model Adopted for Later Calculations for SIFT Micromechanical Model

X Denotes the Longitudinal Direction, Y the Transverse Direction in Each Ply,
and Z the Normal Direction Perpendicular to the Plane of the Laminate

The Two Strain Invariants in the SIFT Failure Theory For Solid Materials

Distortional (von Mises) Strain Invariant:

$$\gamma_{\text{vM}} = \sqrt{\frac{(\varepsilon_1' - \varepsilon_2')^2 + (\varepsilon_1' - \varepsilon_3')^2 + (\varepsilon_2' - \varepsilon_3')^2}{2}}$$

Dilatational (J_1) Strain Invariant:

$$J_1 = \varepsilon_1 + \varepsilon_2 + \varepsilon_3$$

It is necessary to add $3\alpha_m\Delta T$ to the J_1 strain invariant for the matrix to allow for residual thermal stresses.

SIFT Model for Characterization of Strengths of Fibers And Matrix in Terms of Strain Invariants

Effect of Difference between Homogeneous and Heterogeneous Modelling on Sample Size per Coupon

**Homogenized Model,
Single “Material” Throughout**

Sample Size of 1 per Coupon

**Heterogeneous Model.
Millions of Separate Fibres
and Matrix Interstices**

Sample Size of 1,000,000+ per Coupon

Artificial Singularities Created by Omission of Flexible Interlayers from Model of Composite Laminates

Singularities in Interlaminar Shear Stress for Fully Homogenized Unidirectional Plies

No Singularities in Interlaminar Shear Stress when Flexible Interlayer Included

The Actual Interlaminar Shear-Stress Distribution at the Abrupt Termination of Stiff Composite Members

Edge Delaminations, or Worse, Caused by Excessive Blocking of Parallel Plies

AS-4/3501-6 Carbon/Epoxy, 0.005 in. (0.0125 mm) UD Plies

4-Ply Stacks,
45° Angle Changes,
No Delaminations

4-Ply Stacks,
45° and 90° Angle Changes,
Some Delaminations

Thick 8-Ply Stacks,
45° Angle Changes,
Total Delaminations

Concluding Remarks

Prediction of matrix failures based on analyses at the homogenized lamina level have been found to be unreliable, resulting in unanticipated premature failures, program delays, cost over-runs, and increased in-service inspections.

Most composite analysts are unaware that it is either necessary or even possible to predict matrix failures at the constituent level, using intrinsic material properties.

Homogenization of individual plies prevents the calculation of internal residual thermal stresses and strains.

The SIFT (Strain Invariant Failure Theory) is available, and has been validated, to make scientific predictions of matrix failures – *AND* to enable better designs that will *not* fail in the matrix first, allowing the fibres to develop their full strength before final laminate failures.

Constraints need to be placed on designs and laminate fibre patterns to avoid premature failures in the matrix. Terminating stiffeners short of the edges of panels should be absolutely prohibited. The root cause of the problem is excessive clustering of fibres, beyond the capacity of the surrounding resin to shear load in or out of them.

Remember!

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